

Patient safety culture in home care, its antecedents, and outcomes: A scoping review protocol

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Abstract

Objective: The objectives of this scoping review will be to 1) map the available evidence on patient safety culture/climate assessment tools and 2) to assess antecedents and outcomes related to patient safety culture/climate in home care.

Introduction: For the maintenance of safe healthcare systems, both for patients and staff, safety culture/climate has gained increasing importance. A culture of safety is an essential component of a healthy work environment that enables staff to deliver high-quality and safe healthcare. The focus of reviews on patient safety culture/climate has been predominantly within hospital settings. Understanding which instruments have been used to measure patient safety culture/climate in home care and which factors have been associated with safety culture/climate will inform future research and practitioners on measurement tools and on strategies to improve safety culture/climate.

Inclusion criteria: Studies will be considered eligible if they report on instruments/measures to assess patient safety culture/climate. We will include safety culture/climate, its antecedents and outcomes reported by healthcare professionals working in home care, i.e., at patients' homes. Studies with quantitative, qualitative or mixed-methods designs will be included.

Methods: The scoping review will follow the framework by Arksey and O'Malley. We will systematically search MEDLINE/PubMed, CINAHL, PsycINFO/Ovid, Embase/Ovid, and Web of Science. Additionally, we will conduct backward/forward citation tracking of the included studies to identify further relevant articles. Identified studies will be independently screened by two reviewers against the eligibility criteria. Findings will be mapped and described in narrative and tabular format.

Keywords: patient safety, surveys and questionnaires, safety management, organizational culture

Introduction

Unsafe care resulting in unintended patient harm and adverse events accounts for 15% of health spending in OECD countries (1). With the publication of landmark reports like “To Err is Human” (2) and more recently the COVID-19 pandemic, the awareness of patient safety has become widely acknowledged as an ethical, economic and public health concern driving the need for research and improvement initiatives (1). To maintain safe healthcare systems, both for patients and workers, safety culture has gained increasing prominence. The World Health Organization (WHO) Global Patient Safety Action Plan 2021-2030 emphasizes the need to “instill a safety culture in the design and delivery of health care” and urges governments to “adopt global approaches for establishment of a safety culture across the health system, including building competencies in methods for culture change” (3).

Safety culture and safety climate have been defined differently at times and used interchangeably. Safety climate is a surface manifestation of patient safety culture, defined by the shared perceptions and attitudes held by members of a team or organization about the way safety is managed and valued within the organization (4, 5). Safety culture is a pattern of individual and organizational behavior based on shared perceptions and beliefs. It has been described as more complex and difficult to measure, consisting of three layers. The core layer represents the basic and fundamental assumptions about safety, the middle consists of the values, beliefs and attitudes and the outer layer represents the behavioral manifestations of the underlying safety culture (5). Safety climate is thus the perceptions of the outer and middle layer of safety culture at a given time (6).

While there are reviews that have reported on patient safety culture/climate assessment tools in specific healthcare settings, there is no overview of the instruments used in home care. Furthermore, to the best of our knowledge, there is no review of the factors associated with patient safety culture/climate in home care. Given the distinctive nature of the home care setting, where care is provided at patient’s homes, it’s important to understand how patient safety culture/climate is been assessed in this setting. Mapping the existing instruments is crucial to guide both researchers and practitioners in measuring safety culture/climate in home care. To identify which antecedents and outcomes have been analyzed related to patient safety culture/climate is essential for the understanding of safety culture/climate in home care, to inform the design of interventions to improve safety culture/climate and identify gaps in research.

An exploratory search of MEDLINE/PubMed, PROSPERO, and Open Science Framework (OSF) was conducted, and no current or ongoing systematic reviews or scoping reviews on patient safety culture/climate in home care were identified.

Review question(s)

This scoping review aims to provide an overview of the existing instruments measuring patient safety culture/climate and its associated factors in the home care setting. Specifically, we aim to answer the following questions:

- 1) What instruments/assessment tools have been used to measure patient safety culture/climate in home care, rated by healthcare professionals?
- 2) What dimensions, items, topics, or themes do these patient safety culture/climate instruments include?
- 3) What antecedents and outcomes have been analyzed in relationship with patient safety culture/climate in home care?

Eligibility criteria

Participants

We will include studies that involve health, social care professionals or home care employees working in home care, i.e., providing care/support at patient's homes. Studies in the home care setting excluding social or clinical care staff will be excluded.

Concept

Studies assessing patient safety culture, patient safety climate, or patient safety attitudes, regardless of the definition/conceptualization used will be included.

Context

We will include studies that measure patient safety culture/climate from the perspective of healthcare professionals providing care or treatment in home care. Studies conducted in community settings other than including care/treatment at patients' homes (e.g., exclusively in nursing homes, pharmacies) will be excluded.

Types of sources

This scoping review will include original research that used a quantitative, qualitative or mixed-methods design. We will exclude case series and individual case reports. Studies where the full text is not available, comments, letters, discussion papers and editorials will be excluded. No restriction on date or language will be applied.

Methods

The scoping review will follow the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) methodology for scoping reviews (7) and the framework by Arksey and O'Malley (8).

Search strategy

The search strategy aims to locate only published studies. As a first step, a limited search of MEDLINE/PubMed was conducted to identify articles on safety culture/climate. The text words found in the titles and abstracts of relevant articles, as well as the index terms used to describe the articles, were used to develop a full search strategy for MEDLINE/PubMed (see Appendix A). The initial search strategy was revised with the support of an information specialist. The search strategy will be adapted for the other databases using Polyglot Search Translator (<https://sr-accelerator.com/#/polyglot>) and through manual adjustments. We will search for evidence in the following electronic databases: Medical Literature Analysis and Retrieval System Online (MEDLINE/PubMed), Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL), PsycINFO via Ovid, EMBASE via Ovid, and Web of Science. Snowballing through backward and forward citation tracking of the included studies will be used to search for additional studies.

Study selection

Studies will be extracted, duplicates removed, and screened in Covidence (9). In a first step, following a pilot test of 50 records, two researchers will independently screen all titles and abstracts for eligibility. In a second step, studies judged to be potentially relevant will be retrieved, and their full-text will be screened applying the predefined in- and exclusion criteria. Any disagreements between the reviewers at any stage of the selection process will be resolved through discussion with a third, more senior reviewer. Reasons for exclusion of articles at full text that do not meet the inclusion criteria will be recorded and reported in the scoping review. The results of the search and the study inclusion process will be reported in the final scoping in a Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses extension for scoping review (PRISMA-ScR) flow diagram (10). To manage the references, we will use Endnote (version 20) (11).

Data extraction

Data will be extracted from articles included in the scoping review by two independent reviewers using a data extraction form developed by the reviewers. Data extraction will be performed in Covidence (9). The information extracted will include authors, year of publication, study design, population, reported instrument, dimensions covered by the instrument, antecedents, outcomes, and comments by the reviewers. The extraction form will be piloted and adapted with the first 5 studies. All decision steps and modifications to the initial data extraction form will be documented and reported in the scoping review. If

data extraction of results is unclear or incomplete, we will not contact study authors to obtain the missing data due to time restraints.

Data synthesis

We will conduct a descriptive synthesis of the studies found. Data will be presented in tabular form. A narrative summary will accompany the tabulated results.

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Ethical considerations and dissemination

No ethical approval required as we will only use data from previous published research. The study findings will be disseminated through a peer-reviewed publication and discussions with key stakeholders and conference presentations.

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Conflicts of interest

There is no conflict of interest in this project.

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Appendix A

Search strategy

Table A1. Search string for MEDLINE/PubMed

Block A (primary care / community care / home care)	"Home Care Agencies"[Mesh] OR "homecare agencies"[tiab] OR "homecare agency"[tiab] OR "home health agencies"[tiab] OR "home health agency"[tiab] OR "Home Care Services"[Mesh] OR "homecare services"[tiab] OR "homecare service"[tiab] OR "home health care"[tiab] OR "home healthcare"[tiab] OR "home care"[tiab] OR "House Calls"[Mesh] OR "house call"[tiab] OR "house calls"[tiab] OR "home visit"[tiab] OR "home visits"[tiab] OR "home visitation"[tiab] OR "home visitations"[tiab] OR "home visitor"[tiab] OR "home visitors"[tiab] OR "Community Health Services"[Mesh:NoExp] OR "community health service"[tiab] OR "community health services"[tiab] OR "community care"[tiab] OR "community health care"[tiab] OR "community healthcare"[tiab] OR "community health centers"[tiab] OR "community health centre"[tiab] OR "community health centres"[tiab] OR "Community Health Centers"[Mesh:NoExp] OR "Primary Health Care"[Mesh:NoExp] OR "Primary Health Care"[tiab] OR "primary healthcare"[tiab] OR "primary care"[tiab] OR "domiciliary care"[tiab] OR "domestic healthcare"[tiab] OR "domestic health care"[tiab]
Block B (safety culture/climate)	"safety management"[Mesh:NoExp] OR ("organizational culture"[Mesh] AND ("safety"[Mesh:NoExp] OR "patient safety"[Mesh])) OR "safety culture"[tiab] OR "safety climate"[tiab] OR "culture of safety"[tiab] OR "safety attitude"[tiab] OR "safety attitudes"[tiab] OR "safety management"[tiab]
Combination	(Block A) AND (Block B)

Note. Mesh, Medical Subject Headings; tiab, Title/Abstract